

Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) studies on sulphide analogues as potent M₂ muscarinic receptor antagonists

A. K. Srivastava*, A. A. Khan, Abha Tripathi and Archana

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

E-mail : qsarlab@rediffmail.com

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QSAR studies on sulphide analogues (1-12) of M₂ muscarinic receptor antagonists for the treatment of cognitive disorder are reported. The activity of compound 1 (1-naphthyl) is found to be most potent analogue of the series as shown by electronic, hydrophobic and steric factors.

Muscarinic receptors are present in the central and peripheral nervous system as well as in organs innervated by the autonomic nervous system. These receptors play an important role in a wide range of different functions, such as central control of movement and cognition as well as in the peripheral control of smooth muscle tone and glandular secretion¹.

We report here the correlation of antagonistic activity of sulphide analogues with physicochemical parameters with a view to provide a better rational approach for the future drug designing. The electronic parameter Xeq (equalised electronegativity)² hydrophobic parameter log P (Partition coefficient)³ and steric parameter ¹χ^v (molecular connectivity)⁴ have been used, in order to describe the role of different properties such as electronic, structural and hydrophobic nature of the drug molecules on the activity. The regression analysis was performed with the help of statistical programme SPSS 7.5 Version.

Results and discussion

M₂ muscarinic receptor antagonists sulphide analogues (1-12) and their activity (pk_i) data are listed in Table 1 along with the values of physicochemical parameters.

The linear correlation of pk_i with Xeq, ¹χ^v and log P are given below.

$$pk_i = -20.898 (\pm 62.433) Xeq + 54.957 \quad (1)$$

$n = 12, R = 0.230, R^2 = 0.053, R_A^2 = 0.04, F_{(1,10)} = 0.556, S.E. = 0.742$

$$pk_i = 0.235 (\pm 0.508) {}^1\chi^v + 3.817 \quad (2)$$

$n = 12, R = 0.310, R^2 = 0.096, R_A^2 = 0.006, F_{(1,10)} = 1.065, S.E. = 0.0725$

$$pk_i = 0.065 (\pm 0.267) \log P + 6.537 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 12, R = 0.169, R^2 = 0.028, R_A^2 = -0.069, F_{(1,10)} = 0.292, S.E. = 0.752$$

where n represents the number of data points, R is the correlation coefficient, R^2 is the coefficient of determination, R_A^2 is the adjusted R^2 , also known as explained variance (EV) which when multiplied by 100 gives the percentage of the variance in activity that can be accounted for by the equation, $S.E.$ the standard error of estimate, F the variance ratio between the calculated and observed activities and data with (\pm) sign in parenthesis is confidence interval. Above given liner regressions gave very poor correlations as it is evident from the values of the statistical terms.

Correlation level was found to improve considerably when 1-naphthyl was introduced as indicator I_1 at position Ar with the above mentioned parameters. The resulting equations are

$$pk_i = 10.371 (\pm 23.136) Xeq + 2.475 (\pm 0.64) I_1 - 17.20 \quad (4)$$

$n = 12, R = 0.949, R^2 = 0.900, R_A^2 = 0.88, F_{(2,9)} = 40.632, S.E. = 0.253$

$$pk_i = 0.069 (\pm 0.188) {}^1\chi^v + 2.32 (\pm 0.628) I_1 + 5.77 \quad (5)$$

$n = 17, R = 0.947, R^2 = 0.897, R_A^2 = 0.874, F_{(2,9)} = 39.126, S.E. = 0.258$

$$pk_i = 0.061 (\pm 0.142) \log P + 2.361 (\pm 1.091) I_1 + 6.589 \quad (6)$$

$n = 12, R = 0.944, R^2 = 0.891, R_A^2 = 0.866, F_{(2,9)} = 36.645, S.E. = 0.266$

In the above given eqs. (4), (5) and (6), R^2 , adjusted R_A^2

be preferred in future drug designing.

The (+)ve sign of coefficients of X_{eq} , ${}^1\chi^v$ and $\log P$ indicates that more electronegative, bulkier and hydrophobic groups may tend to increase the activity.

It may be concluded that in future drug designing following points should be kept in mind.

- (i) The more hydrophobic substituent should be preferable.
- (ii) The activity of M_2 antagonists is highly influenced due to the presence of 1-naphthyl group at heteroaryl moiety (Ar) of the sulphide analogues.
- (iii) The larger groups which are more electronegative

should be conducive in further drug modeling.

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